

LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE
FOR SCIENTIFIC ARTICLES PUBLICATION

No. 02/JPR/LoA/6-VIII/2024

Chief of Editor Jurnal Psikologi Revolusioner (JPR) has decided that the name article below has been accepted on JPR and will be published in Vol 8 No 6 2024.

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MASA COVID-19 SMP PERCUT SEI TUAN
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Thank you for submitting your article to our journal. We wish you all possible success in the future.

Warm regards,

Jurnal Psikologi Revolusioner
Chief Editor